

1 **A putative molecular mechanism for penetrating function of TNFSF14 (LIGHT) involving matrix**
2 **metalloproteinase activity.**

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7 We recently identified TNFSF14 (LIGHT) as a stage selective switch in the human myeloid compartment
8 that regulated the MDP-responsive gene expression program. We used a synthetic transcriptional network
9 to study and identify gene interaction partners functioning as effectors of molecular mechanism in a
10 human disease. Transcriptional profiling of a TNFRSF14 centered network identified an MMP cluster with
11 potential for penetrating activity. The MMP module included MMP25 and MMP9.

12 Citations

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